

Studies On Insecticidal Plants: Chemical Examination of *Leucas aspera* Spreng

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The whole plant of *Leucas aspera* Spreng. (Fam. *Labiatae*), is reported to possess insecticidal¹ properties. The presence of alkaloids and glycosides in the leaves of this plant was reported earlier². We now report the isolation of oleanolic acid and ursolic acid, characterised as their methylester acetates, and β -sitosterol from the whole plant of *L. aspera*.

Air-dried powdered whole plant of *L. aspera* was extracted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°). The gummy residue left after removal of the solvent was dissolved in large volume of ether and was separated into acidic and neutral fractions in the usual way. The acidic part was directly esterified with diazomethane and the crude methylester thus obtained was chromatographed over a column of silica gel using benzene as the eluent. The benzene eluates furnished a crystalline solid of m.p. 110°, which responded to positive Libermann-Burchard colour reaction for triterpenes. This compound was then acetylated and the reaction product was chromatographed over a column of silica gel when two crystalline solids having m.p.s 200-210° (compound A) and 215-225° (compound B) respectively were obtained in poor yields. The compounds A and B on recrystallisation from methanol containing a little chloroform melted at 216-218° and 238-240° respectively. These two triterpenes were identified as oleanolic acid methylester acetate (lit.³, m p. 219-220°) and ursolic acid methylester acetate (lit.,³ m p 243-244°) respectively by m p., m.m.p., TLC, and IR spectra. The neutral fraction on chromatography over a column of silica gel furnished a crystalline sterol which after crystallisation from a mixture of acetone and methanol melted at 135-137°; acetate, m p. 125-127°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.p., m.m p., TLC, IR) with authentic samples

We are currently investigating the matured plants of *L aspera* in search of other chemical constituents.

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